

IN-SITU MEASUREMENTS OF STRUCTURAL DAMAGE IN NOTCHED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Prediction of matrix failure in composite laminates typically uses computational methods based on material strength and material toughness. The two approaches are often used separately, and the effects of damage mode interactions are not included in failure predictions. In presence of complex failure patterns that occur in laminates, failure theories based on the material properties measured in standard experiments may lead to inaccurate predictions. Recent advances in high-resolution non-destructive evaluation methods such as 3D X-ray Computed Tomography led to fundamental change in defect analysis methods by allowing high-fidelity detection of defects in composites and automatic transition of the defect information to structural analysis models. In this work we used customized Computed Tomography system with an internal installation of 11,000 lbs-capable load frame. Two rotational stages are automatically controlled with high angular precision positioning for in-situ CT scans. The facility was utilized for measuring crack front advancing under load in composite Double Cantilever Beam specimens used as standard test to determine Mode I fracture toughness. The objective of this work is to investigate in-situ development of structural damage around notches in composite laminates based on high fidelity three-dimensional CT measurements under static loading up to a specimen failure. The technical challenges of this analysis are the ability to accurately measure structural defects in three dimensions and then accurately model the sub-surface defect geometry in structural models. FE models that include highly detailed modeling of structural defects can be used to calculate strain energy release rates for actual structural defect geometries and assess the applicability of failure theories that use fracture toughness properties measured in standard tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Prediction of matrix failure in composite laminates, including both intra- and interlaminar failure, typically uses computational methods based on material strength and material toughness [1-2]. The two approaches are often used separately, and the effects of damage mode interactions are not included in failure predictions. Material property measurements are usually performed on specimens that localize one failure mode and minimize interactions from the other types of damage. Toughness properties are typically measured starting from relatively large pre-cracks. In the presence of complex failure patterns that occur in laminates, failure theories based on the material properties measured in these experiments may not represent the same failure conditions.

Recent advances in high-resolution non-destructive evaluation methods such as 3D X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) led to fundamental change in defect analysis methods by allowing high-fidelity detection of defects in composites and automatic transition of the defect information to structural analysis models [3]. The authors have published number of works on using X-Ray CT for failure analysis in presence of manufacturing defects [4-6]. In this work, X-Ray CT is shown to provide new capabilities in detection of accurate sub-surface geometry of structural defects, such as matrix cracks and delaminations, and transition of these measurements to structural models.

In this work we used an X5000 X-Ray CT system manufactured by North Star Imaging customized with the internal installation of 11,000 lbs (50 kN) capable electromechanical load frame shown in Figure 1. Two rotational stages are automatically controlled with high angular precision positioning

for in-situ CT scans. Micro-focus CT system used in this work is able to detect structural defects of less than 10 μm in thickness for coupon-sized articles.

The in-situ CT scanning facility was utilized for measuring crack front advancing under load in Carbon/Epoxy composite Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens used as standard test for Mode I fracture toughness allowable. The standard fracture toughness measurements are compared with finite element (FE)-based calculations that use high fidelity sub-surface measurements of curved crack fronts.

The objective of this work is to investigate the in-situ development of structural damage in notched composite laminates based on high fidelity three-dimensional CT measurements under static loading up to a specimen failure. The technical challenges of this analysis are the ability to accurately measure structural defects in three dimensions and subsequent accurate modeling of the sub-surface defect geometry in structural models. FE models that include high detailed modeling of structural defects, including both matrix cracks and delaminations, can be used to calculate strain energy release rates for detected structural defect geometries and assess the applicability of failure theories based on fracture toughness properties measured in standard tests.

Figure 1: Customized X5000 X-Ray micro-focus CT facility and the integrated load frame enabling full CT scanning under loading.

2 DAMAGE DETECTION BY THE X-RAY CT UNDER COMPRESSIVE LOAD

Simulation of crack development in fiber-reinforced composite Open-Hole Compression (OHC) specimens is important to investigate progressive failure in load-bearing composite joint elements. As many analytical and computational models that characterize failure under compression have been proposed, a comparison of failure patterns with experimental data is key to assess their predictive qualities. However, since composite laminate articles demonstrate complex sub-surface failure patterns including matrix cracks and delaminations, such comparison requires reliable three-dimensional evaluation. X-ray Computed Tomography is a proven non-destructive evaluation technique that satisfies the above requirements. Since X-Ray CT method uses spatial density contrast to detect boundaries between different media the crack detection quality depends on having a crack opening that is comparable to voxel size of the scan. If fracture surfaces close during unloading of the specimens it may prevent reliable damage detection in the CT scans.

To alleviate this problem a load frame was installed [7] to perform CT scans while specimens were under the compressive load. A conceptual drawing for the load frame used in X-ray CT is shown in Figure 2. As illustrated, the specimen is suspended between the grips, which are mounted on two rotating stages moving synchronously to allow for computed tomography projections to be recorded. This allows for simultaneous loading and rotation of the specimen. Also, since the actuation of each rotation stage is independent of the other, the machine can also be used to apply torsional loads on the specimen. This can be achieved by offsetting the rotation stages from each other by the required torque / angle, then synchronizing the stages allowing for CT scans.

Figure 2: Conceptual drawing [15] and a photograph of the load frame for the X-ray CT system.

See Ref. [7] for technical details of the load frame installation and performance.

12-ply [0/-45/90/45]_{S3} Carbon/Epoxy IM7/8552 OHC specimens were manufactured and tested under quasi-static load per ASTM D6484 specifications [8]. Digital Image Correlation technique was used for monitoring surface strains and progression of surface-ply cracks. Quasi-static compressive loading of the specimen was stopped at 10,000 lbs (44.5 kN) when fiber failure in the zero degree surface ply is well developed and visible but before the ultimate structural failure of the laminate. The specimens were then subject to post-failure non-destructive inspection with the North Star X-Ray micro-CT system. Figure 3 shows the 3D reconstruction results for an OHC specimen after the applied compressive loading [9]. A fiber failure crack develops in the 0-degree surface-ply from both side of the hole with matrix-cracks and delaminations along the crack path. Fiber failure accompanied by matrix cracks and delamination was also found in the adjacent plies, although less visible.

Figure 3: 3D CT reconstruction of OHC specimen showing structural damage after 10,000 lbs (44.5 kN) compressive loading.

The fiber-aligned sub-model around the hole of the OHC specimen was used for FE simulation of the failure progression. The analysis was performed using ABAQUS finite element software [10] with custom material procedure UMAT [9]. The analysis showed that failure initiated with matrix compression cracking developing in the zero degree plies around 5000 lbs (22.2 kN), accompanied by

delaminations at the interface with the adjacent ply. The simultaneous development of matrix compression cracks and delaminations suggests strong interaction between the two failure mechanisms as shown in Figure 4. Matrix cracks in the 45-degree plies start to appear around 6000 lbs (26.7 kN) as compression matrix cracks and delaminations develop further in the 0-degree plies. Figure 4 demonstrates that strong interaction is also observed between the matrix cracks and the development of delaminations at the ply interface of the 45-degree plies. Compression matrix failures and delaminations in the surface and sub-surface 0-degree plies lead to compressive fiber failure that initiates around 6600 lbs (29.4 kN). Matrix cracks in the 90-degree plies start to grow around 7800 lbs (34.7 kN). The simulation stopped at 9500 lbs (42.2 kN) as the growth of fiber failure in the surface 0-degree ply led to local buckling in the FE model with large element distortion resulting in difficulties to obtain converged solution [9].

Figure 4: Development of matrix compression cracks and compressive fiber failure (dark grey) and delaminations (lighter grey) in the surface 0° ply (right) and first sub-surface 45° ply (left) [9].

The first attempt to correlate FE simulation results for crack growth and location with 3D CT reconstructions of OHC specimens after 10,000 lbs (44.5 kN) compressive loading seemed to indicate that crack lengths were over-estimated in the numerical model. Also, significant matrix cracks and delaminations were predicted at locations where no apparent damage was visible in the CT data. In fact, only fiber failure in the zero degree plies and delamination in the adjacent plies were observed in the CT reconstructions whereas the FE model predicted matrix cracks and delaminations for each laminate ply groups as shown in Figure 4. Closer local CT inspections using maximal magnification suggested that cracks were probably present at the expected locations but fracture surfaces “closed up” during unloading of the specimens preventing successful damage detection in the CT scans.

The integrated load frame was used to apply a 5000 lbs (22.2 kN) tensile load to the OHC specimens after static tests at 10,000 lbs (44.5 kN). The stabilized displacement suggested that no further damage developed in the specimens due to tensile loading. The tensile load allowed to “open up” the fracture surfaces that appeared during compression loading and many cracks previously undetected in the unloaded specimens became clearly visible. Figure 5 shows the comparison between FE results at 9,500 lbs (42.3 kN) and CT data under tensile load after OHC test at 10,000 lbs (44.5 kN). Excellent correlation between simulation and test data is demonstrated with very good agreement for crack lengths and crack locations of matrix and fiber failures in each ply group of the laminate [9].

Figure 5: Comparison of FE predictions and CT data under load for OHC specimens [9].

3 MEASURING MODE I FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN DOUBLE-CANTILEVER BEAM

Measurement of Mode I fracture toughness in Double-Cantilever Beam (DCB) testing was selected as a benchmark problem for the CT-based measurement technique under the load. In addition to verification of the loading apparatus and the measurement system, testing under CT scan allows determining the shape and the geometry of the crack front and improving the accuracy of fracture toughness measured in the test.

DCB specimens were manufactured according to the guidelines in ASTM D5528 [11] from 24 ply, unidirectional IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy composite. Specimens were then pre-cracked, loaded at a constant rate of 0.05 inch/min, and the load and crack opening displacement at each of the crack progression markings was recorded. Mode I fracture toughness was calculated for three specimens using a Modified Beam Theory method.

To obtain X-ray CT scans for the in-situ DCB testing, a special test fixture was developed [7]. The vertical DCB test fixture is shown in Figure 6. It has a wedge attached to the machine movable cross-head via a threaded connection, two rigid roller assemblies affixed to the specimen sides, and a bottom holder (shaped as wedge) to provide support for the bottom of the specimen.

The procedure for the vertical test was similar to the procedure used in the standard DCB test. The specimens were loaded at a rate of 0.05 inch (1.27 mm) per minute. Photographs taken at different crack length were used to measure crack opening and crack length at the surface for each crack length increment. At each 5 mm crack growth increment the test was paused and a CT scan of the specimen was performed. A 60 KV and 416 μ A technique at 2 frames per second, 720 projections over 360 degrees and 6.59x geometric magnification was used. This resulted in a voxel size (volumetric pixel) of 10 micron, and a scan time of 40 minutes.

All scans were reconstructed using North Star efX-CT software by generating 3D volumetric representation for each 5 mm crack growth in the specimen. To find precise location of the crack front, the density region, the cutting plane position, and the cutting plane yaw and pitch angles were all manipulated until the lowest crack front was visible across the thickness of the specimen. For all cracks from pre-crack to largest crack lengths demonstrated curved crack fronts with the advancing central part of the crack. The crack front curves for all cracks were found to be well approximated

with a circular shape, and therefore an arc was fitted to all the measured fronts in the efX-CT software, and the diameter and the location of the center of the arc was recorded. Figure 7 shows a 2D slice from one of the reconstructed volumes showing the location of the insert and the measurement of the pre-crack curved front.

Figure 6: Vertical DCB test configuration: from left to right - schematic drawing, photograph in the X-ray CT, and an FE model.

A finite element model was developed in ABAQUS software [10] to calculate the strain energy release rates for the tested specimens. The wedge was modeled as an analytical rigid surface and displacement boundary conditions were prescribed to model machine cross-head downward movement. The specimen roller block supports were modeled using 0.1 inch (2.54 mm) section thickness and high stiffness. The contact between the wedge and the rollers was modeled as a frictionless surface-to-surface interaction. Figure 6 demonstrates FE model of the vertical test setup with a curved crack front.

Figure 7: Crack front identification from the CT volume.

An implementation of Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) method used to find strain energy release rates (SERR) for curved crack fronts [12] was used. In this method the area calculation for the VCCT method is based on the virtual orthogonal mesh, and displacement values are interpolated at

projected virtual mesh points. This method was reported to yield results in good agreement (within 3%) with the results by the orthogonal meshes. Figure 8 shows profiles of the cracks through-the-width of the specimen as measured in the CT scans and plotted with respect to the average crack front length in the middle section; and distribution of the SERR values at the same points along curved crack fronts.

Figure 9 compares mode I resistance curves (dependence of the fracture toughness from the delamination length) measured in the experiment using the Modified Beam Theory method specified in ASTM D5528-01, and calculated using VCCT method based on FE meshes built using curved crack front measured using CT scans. In the latter method fracture toughness was determined as the average value along the 40% of the mostly flat SERR plot section located in middle of crack front on Figure 8, right. Other two specimens demonstrated less symmetric distributions along crack front and again, mostly flat 40% of SERR plot section was used to find the average value. For the three specimens, the average Mode I Fracture Toughness value was determined as $G_{IC} = 0.260$ kJ/m² (1.48 in-psi) by the Modified Beam Theory method and as $G_{IC} = 0.283$ kJ/m² (1.61 in-psi) by the CT-FEM-VCCT method. These values compare well with the average value of $G_{IC} = 0.277$ kJ/m² (1.58 in-psi) reported by Camahno and Lambert [13] for IM7/8552 and larger than $G_{IC} = 0.208$ kJ/m² (1.19 in-psi) reported by Hansen and Martin [14].

Figure 8: Crack front profiles (left) and SERR along crack front (right) for different crack increments in DCB specimen 1.

Figure 9: Mode I resistance curves for the three DCB specimens calculated from experiment and using CT-FEM-VCCT method.

4 MIXED MODE FAILURE IN UNIDIRECTIONAL OPEN-HOLE TENSION SPECIMEN

Four unidirectional Carbon/Epoxy composite Open-Hole Tension (OHT) specimens were CT scanned under load to determine strain energy release rates for intralaminar matrix cracks of different lengths and geometries. 6-ply 1-inch (25.4 mm)-wide and 0.5 inch (12.7 mm)-diameter hole IM7/8552 OHT specimens were quasi-statically loaded until failure. While the specimens were loaded the crack development was monitored using live X-ray radiography. Matrix cracks mostly developed through the full thickness of the specimen and were visible in plain X-ray. When significant crack development was detected, the test was stopped and load decreased to 90% of the maximum load; and CT scan was performed under the fixed load. Parameters of the CT scan were selected to scan complete damaged area and maximize the scan speed as multiple scans were needed to monitor cracking progress for a single specimen. Figure 10 shows an example of cracks found in the OHT specimen using CT scan under load. Note that the crack planes may not be perpendicular to the surface of the specimen but oriented at an angle from the through-thickness plane and crack fronts are typically curved.

Figure 10: Crack geometry cracks in the OHT specimen shown by the CT scan under load.

All crack locations, lengths, crack plane orientations and front shapes for all specimens were measured in the 3D volume reconstructions of CT scans. These measurements were used to build finite element mesh with explicit modeling of discontinuities. Explicit modeling of cracks involved the following steps: first, a rectangular structured mesh with fixed element density was built; second, the mesh was morphed in three dimensions to reflect: a) width-wise position of the crack; b) different lengths of the crack on top and bottom surface of the specimen; c) measured crack front shape including cracks that do not span through entire thickness; and d) through-the-thickness inclination angle of the crack plane. Morphing mesh, *i.e.* moving the mesh nodes, is necessary since mesh discontinuity can only be created explicitly at the nodes. Mesh morphing involves moving all mesh nodes in the center area to ensure mesh quality appropriate for structural analysis and avoid element self-intersection. Third, after morphing modifications were completed, the hole geometry was created by: a) deleting elements completely contained in the hole; b) moving remaining nodes to the closest location at the hole surface; and c) converting badly shaped 8-noded elements into 6-noded wedges. Although this method generated some oddly shaped elements on the surface of the hole, it did not prevent analysis from running and these elements did not affect the solution around crack fronts required for the VCCT method calculations. Figure 11 demonstrates the finite element mesh and crack surfaces. Strain energy release rates were calculated for each crack along the fronts using VCCT technique using this FE model under the load that corresponded to this geometric configuration.

Figure 11: FE mesh represents actual damage geometry in the OHT specimen under load.

Figure 12 and 13 show calculated strain energy release rates along the crack fronts for different cracks. For each crack the figures show corresponding crack plane angle α_c and matrix crack geometry such as different cracks length on both surfaces of the specimen and length of the crack front. All crack front extensions are in scale with respect to the thickness t . The dashed line shows the extent of the hole and corresponds to 0.133 in (3.37 mm) crack length as measured from the diameter line of the hole, except for the two cracks in specimen 2 where cracks are too long to maintain scale. Strain energy release rates are plotted with respect to coordinate along crack front x_c divided by specimen thickness.

Figure 12 demonstrates development of strain energy release rates while matrix cracks develop due to increasing loads. Changes in crack lengths are shown on crack geometry plots. For both cracks, fast crack growth is observed for the last load case just before failure; however, while crack (1) lengths change proportionally, crack (4) flips the advancing side, which leads to significant changes in strain energy release rate distributions.

Figure 12: Strain energy release rates (blue: mode I, green: mode II, red: mode III) for 2 cracks in Specimen 1 at growing crack lengths.

Figures 13 shows SERR calculation results for all cracks in all four specimens at the loads closest to failure. For specimen 1 this load was 995 lbs (4.43 kN); for specimen 2: 1000 lbs (4.45 kN); for specimen 3: 830 lbs (3.69 kN); and for specimen 4: 927 lbs (4.12 kN). A few observations can be made from Figure 13. Cracks with mostly straight front are dominated by mode II (green curves in Figure 13). The more curvature is observed in the crack front, the more dominant is the mode III, and for most of the cracks mode II SERR switch to the mode III at different crack front coordinates. Short cracks that are smaller than hole radius also show mode I contribution. The Figure shows that the matrix cracks demonstrate mostly linear growth of fracture toughness with respect to crack length.

The cracks with dominant mode II SERR could be used to determine mode II fracture toughness properties: values were found between 0.4 kJ/m^2 (2.3 in-psi) and 1.1 kJ/m^2 (6.3 in-psi). For comparison the properties found in the 4-point bending end-notched flexure tests are: 0.8 kJ/m^2 (4.6 in-psi) reported by Camahno and Lambert [13] and 1.3 kJ/m^2 (7.4 in-psi) reported by Hansen and Martin [14].

Figure 13: Strain energy release rates (blue: mode I, green: mode II, red: mode III) for all cracks in all specimens at maximum loads.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This work presented the in-situ investigation of development of structural damage around notches in composite laminates based on high fidelity three-dimensional CT measurements under static tensile and compressive loads. In particular, it was demonstrated that the X-ray CT scans under load reveal more complete pattern of structural failures such as matrix cracks, delamination and fiber failure as compared with X-ray CT scans with no load applied. Reconstructions by X-ray CT combined with the load frame have shown improved comparison of experimentally found structural defects and damage simulation results by FE methods. The X-ray facility with the load frame was also used to accurately measure subsurface crack geometry in unidirectional Carbon/Epoxy DCB specimens and OHT specimens. The system was also utilized for measuring Mode I fracture toughness in the DCB tests and then used for calculation of strain energy release rates for intralaminar matrix cracks in the OHT test specimens.

Accurate subsurface three-dimensional measurements of damage progression in OHT specimens under loading suggested that crack features, such as crack front geometry and crack length and

location with respect to the notch, are strongly related to fracture mode-mixity, with all three fracture modes involved. This result suggests that an appropriate mixed-mode fracture criterion as well as dependency on the crack length should be considered for the accurate prediction of the intralaminar failure propagation in OHT specimens.

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